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Implementation of the New Public Service in the Licensing Process

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Abstract

This study discusses the implementation of the principles of the New Public Service (NPS) in the public service of the Bekasi City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Service, by taking a case study of making a building permit (IMB) for hotels and restaurants, which is motivated by the findings of BPK-RI audit report dated July 5, 2019 Number 01/XVIII.BKS/07/2019 on the service performance and supervision of the Bekasi City DPMPTSP. Therefore, the problem in this research is: the implementation of licensing by the apparatus at the Bekasi City DPMPTSP in making the IMB has not been effective because it does not use the New Public Service principle. This study aims to critically analyze why the implementation of licensing by the state apparatus in the Bekasi City DPMPTSP is not effective, so it is hoped that a new concept will be born as a solution to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of licensing by state officials at the Bekasi City DPMPTSP on the basis of the New Public Service (NPS) paradigm. The research method used is a qualitative method with case study techniques, through collecting data from primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained from 10 informants, and secondary data was obtained from various documents, journals, scientific works, and others. The results of the study indicate that the implementation of licensing by the State apparatus in DPMPTSP Bekasi City is not effective

Keywords: New Public Service, Building Permit, One-Stop Integrated Service, Bekasi City, Licensing

1. Introduction

Providing quality public services is an important part of governance and public administration, both at the central and regional levels. Even how the government provides public services is a mirror of clean and good governance. Public service is one of the variables that is a measure of the success of the implementation of regional autonomy. If the public services carried out by the regional government are good quality, then the implementation of regional autonomy can be said to be successful. However, the quality of public services in the New Order era tends to show a tendency to deteriorate. Public services tend to be poor because the central government intervenes too much in local governments in the delivery of public services in the regions. This causes local governments to be unable to take initiative and initiative when providing public services to their citizens (Dwiyanto et al, 2020).

The implementation of public services which is a real picture of the government's performance in providing services to the community has not run optimally so that the quality of apparatus services is still in the spotlight,

especially regarding service procedures and procedures that are felt to be long and convoluted, there is no certainty of service, both time, cost and requirements, lack of information disclosure on matters related to services (Russel & Byuma, 2001; Ian Sanderson (1996); Abdul Rahim, 2018; and Ahmad Juhari, Willy Tri Hardianto, 2017).

[Russell & Bvuma's \(2001\) research](#) entitled Alternative service delivery and public service transformation in South Africa. [International Journal of Public Sector Management](#). Vol. 14 No. 3. Pp. 241-265. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09513550110390819>. This study reviews the development of public services and outlines several promising alternative service delivery pilot projects. The country of South Africa only emerged in 1994. This new government previously inherited national public services and public services from different provinces and homelands that had to be combined to form a national unified public service. Although this task was completed quickly, the resulting public services were substantial, and demonstrated many features of traditional bureaucracy, including hierarchical structures, limited automation and IT applications, low levels of training, poor work culture, language and cultural barriers, and an overall orientation towards inputs and processes rather than service delivery and outcomes. In the first three years of the new order, substantial efforts were devoted to reforming the bureaucracy. New public service laws and regulations were introduced, new and powerful central staffing bodies were formed, English became the language of administration, and substantial authority was delegated to departments and provinces. Despite these reforms, progress in improving outcomes in terms of service delivery, especially for previously disadvantaged communities, remains mixed. Towards the end of the 1990s, increased attention was paid to ways of improving service delivery. Three important initiatives in this regard were conveyed by Batho Pele (1997), that the application of eight national principles for better service delivery; public-private partnership initiative (2000) and promotion of alternative service delivery. While alternative service delivery initiatives are largely at the pilot stage, they offer promising alternatives both to traditional bureaucracies (with poor cost and service delivery focus) and to narrow versions of privatization (which can involve large social costs, job losses, and declining wealth redistribution). This paper reviews these developments and outlines some promising alternative service delivery pilot projects.

Ian Sanderson's (1996) research entitled Evaluation, learning and the effectiveness of public services: Towards a quality of public service model. [International Journal of Public Sector Management](#). ISSN: 0951-3558. Attempts to discover the nature of the legitimacy of quality discourse within the broader context of prevailing ideas about the role of government in promoting social welfare and how public service organizations can deliver quality services. Outlines the prevailing conventional wisdom underlying the "New Right" project to restructure public services. Provides a critique of this conventional wisdom that addresses the limitations of the "consumerist" notion of the quality and role of rational instrumental discourse in legitimizing the New Right project for state restructuring. Develop alternative conceptions of public service quality and finally outline the role of evaluation in promoting social learning as a basis for achieving effectiveness in public services.

Muhammad Abdul Rahim's research (2018) on the Quality of Public Services in the Field of Licensing and Non-Licensing B Services at the Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Office (DPMPTSP) of Bandung City. This research is motivated by the Bandung City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Agency (DPMPTSP) is an institution that holds strategic roles and functions in the field of implementing integrated licensing services in the City of Bandung, which was formed based on Bandung City Regional Regulation Number 08 of 2016 concerning the Establishment and Arrangement of Bandung City Regional Equipment. The provision of DPMPTSP Bandung City services is required to provide fast, accurate licensing services, at costs according to the provisions, transparently to the people of Bandung City. This research uses the theory presented by Tjiptono, namely the tangible dimension (*tangibles*), the dimension of reliability (*reliability*), the dimension of response (*responsiveness*), the dimension of assurance (*assurance*), and the dimension of empathy (*emphaty*). This research was conducted using qualitative research methods and descriptive survey approach. The result of this study is that DPMPTSP Bandung City has done well what must be done in public services. Supporting factors in public services at DPMPTSP Bandung City include registration of permits using an *online* system, very adequate infrastructure and infrastructure, and adequate quality of human resources. Inhibiting factors in public services at DPMPTSP Bandung City, including the lack of direct socialization to the community from DPMPTSP Bandung City and the quality of Human Resources (HR) business actors in Bandung City on average are still not used to using online systems. The difference with Muhammad Abdul Rahim's (2018) research lies in the focus of research

on licensing and non-business licensing services, while the focus of this research is to focus on the implementation of NPS principles in public services of the DPMPSTSP apparatus.

Research by Ahmad Juhari, Willy Tri Hardianto (2017) on the Quality of Public Services on Restaurant Business Establishment Permits in Batu City. Licensing to establish a restaurant business is one type of licensing service provided to people in need by the Investment Office of PTSP and NAKER Batu City. The large number of people who have a restaurant business establishment permit in Batu City shows that the services provided are in accordance with the expectations of the community. The research method used is qualitative, data collection through observation, interviews and documentation. The results showed that the quality of services provided by the Investment Office of PTSP and NAKER Batu City seen from the ease of obtaining a business license had been said to be good, speed is also good, punctuality is also good, human resources owned are good, facilities are good, security and responsibility are good, operational vehicles are not good, Because there is only 1 (one) unit of operational vehicles, the availability of manpower in the field of business licensing services is not good, because there are 2 (two) people who have been transferred to the position, and the replacement of the two people does not yet exist. The difference with the research of Ahmad Juhari and Willy Tri Hardianto (2017) lies in the focus of research on restaurant business licensing services, while the focus of this research is to focus on the implementation of NPS principles in public services of DPMPSTSP apparatus

Public services are grouped into three types, namely administrative services, goods services, and service services. Administrative licensing services in Indonesia still have problems, ranging from convoluted, unclear processes to difficult access to services obtained and inefficient and effective. This can be seen in the implementation of building permit (IMB) services involving many government agencies and sectoral egos between government agencies (Kurniadi & Suryadi, 2020).

Based on the Ombudsman survey from 2016-2020, there are 8 (eight) regions in West Java Province that are included in the green zone in the implementation of public services, namely Bandung City, Sukabumi City, Garut Regency, Depok City, Bekasi City, and Bogor City (Ombudsman, 2021). For example, the problems found in the Building Permit (IMB) service in Bekasi City, namely:

1. Public services are not charged but in fact there are still levies;
2. Licensing service processes that are delayed too long or not in accordance with the time specified in the mandatory components of public service standards;
3. IMB services are complicated and not simple, so they are inefficient and do not consider fairness in service delivery
4. The costs / rates incurred by the community vary greatly depending on who serves.
5. The process of building permit (IMB) services is not in accordance with the promised deadline. If people want a faster process, we usually get additional fees / tariffs.
6. The attitude of employees who have not fully behaved professionally in carrying out their duties, this can be seen from employees who are less responsive in serving community complaints who experience difficulties during the implementation of building permits (IMB).
7. Inadequate facilities and infrastructure, such as the location of the DPMPSTSP office building within the Bekasi City Government Office, so it is not easily accessible to the community, then the condition of the building is also not fully designed to provide one-stop services (<http://www.bekasikota.go.id/category/6/saran-keluhan>)

The existing condition of public services in Bekasi City still uses the *Old Public Administration* (OPA) approach so that public services do not yet reflect the public services required by the perspective of New Public Service (NPS). The involvement of citizens in policy formulation-implementation-evaluation is pseudo-national; The state apparatus is unresponsive to public aspirations; The state apparatus says more than listens; *Networking* is not built because it is founded by the egos of their respective divisions (work units). Conceptually, the involvement of citizens in policy formulation-implementation-evaluation should not be pseudo, this is because citizen involvement in policy formulation is not dominant, the entire process of developing development policies has not been fully accompanied by various forms of public consultation, and in the implementation and evaluation of development policies, the involvement of new citizens is limited to being beneficiaries, not yet fully needed as one of the actors or part of stakeholders in various development processes. Therefore, Denhardt & Denhardt (2003:

190) suggest that a mechanism be built in the government bureaucracy to accommodate the role of the community as citizens so that the community is always involved in every policy making, both at the formulation, implementation, and policy evaluation stages.

In Dwiyanto's view (2006: 29), poor public services are related to the culture and traditions that exist in bureaucratic performance, especially regarding the mentality of officials that affect work patterns in the workplace. Therefore, strategic steps are needed to change the OPA paradigm that has been used in the bureaucracy towards the use of the NPS perspective. Through the *New Public Service* paradigm based on democratic theory, it is hoped that Bekasi City public services will be more effective in providing services to citizens.

Denhardt & Denhardt (2003), propose 7 principles of public service that refer to the perspective of New Public Service, namely:

- 1) Serve citizens, not customers;.
- 2) Seek the public interest;
- 3) Value citizenship and public service above entrepreneurship;
- 4) Think strategically, act democratically;.
- 5) Recognize that accountability isn't simple;.
- 6) Serve, rather than steer;
- 7) Value people, not just productivity

The findings above show that the issue of licensing implementation has a high complexity and level of difficulty in solving the problem. It requires the involvement of many parties in solving licensing problems. For this reason, in this study will be used the perspective of New Public Service (NPS) as a differentiator from other studies because it uses a relatively more renewable perspective of public administration compared to other public administrations. The concept offered by NPS is that stakeholder involvement in the administration of public affairs is very important. The state and government are no longer the only institutions or stakeholders capable of efficiently, economically, and fairly providing various forms of public services, but also see the importance of partnerships and networking between stakeholders in the administration of public affairs (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2003; Robinson, 2015).

1.1. Problem Statement

Based on the background, the formulation of this research problem is: How are the principles of public services used in making Hotel and Restaurant Building Permits in Bekasi City?

1.2. Research Objectives

This study aims to analyze the principles of public services in making Building Permits (IMB) for Hotels and Restaurants in Bekasi City

2. Literature Review

2.1. New Public Service

The implementation of New Public Management (NPM) in the public sector is not in line with the principles of public service. A number of experts have criticized the NPM, including Kamensky (1996) in his article entitled *The Role of Reinventing Government Movement in Federal Management Reform* published in the *Journal of Public Administration Review*; Box (1999) wrote an article titled *Running Government Like a Business: Implication for Public Administration for Theory and Practice* in the journal *The American Review of Public Administration*; Harrow (2002) with an article entitled *New Public Management and Social Justice: Just Efficiency or Equity as Well?*; Denhardt and Denhardt (2003) in their book *The New Public Service, Serving not Steering*; Haque (2007) with his article *Revisiting New Public Management* published in the journal *Public Administration Review*. These criticisms can be summarized in the form of a table as follows:

Table 1: Criticism of The New Public Management

Researchers	Criticism
Kamensky (1996)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Some bureaucrats tend to compete for their own interests rather than the public interest, and collaborate to achieve this, 2) The first trend occurs because the basis of NPM is the theory of Public Choice which is very dominated by self-interest, 3) NPM tends to ignore the concepts of public spirit, public service, and so on.
Box (1999)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The emergence of NPM has threatened the core value of the public sector, namely citizen selfgovernance and the function of administrators as servants of public interest,
Harrow (2002)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) NPM that ignores public spirit, public service, and so on, will not encourage the democratic process, 2) NPM was never aimed at addressing equity and social justice issues;
Denhardt & Denhardt (2003)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The government must be a public servant (citizen), not just as a director. 2) Government should not be run like a business, but should be run in a democratic manner. 3) In the process, public servants relate to the community being served and servants need to realize that they must listen to the community rather than tell. 4) Society and government work together to determine and present problems together for the common good.
Haque (2007)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) If you are not careful, it will increase corruption and create new poor people.

Source: Processing by Researchers (2023)

According to Denhardt & Denhardt (2003: 28-29), incorporating business values into public organizations has damaged the value order of public administration. Therefore they propose the application of new values. What is considered new from this perspective is to return the party served from the "customer" to its actual position of citizen. Returning the role of government in the perspective of new public management only as a guide to a position that acts as a public servant. The mechanism used to achieve the goal is to build coalitions and cooperation of government, private and civil society institutions, to meet mutually agreed needs. The new value of the accountability approach is a multi-faceted approach, public servants must meet legal provisions, community values, political norms, professionals and the interests of citizens. Its organizational structure is collaborative with shared leadership both internally and externally. The basis of public service motivation is service to society, the desire to contribute to society.

Table 2: NPM Principle Shift to NPS

Aspects	Shifting Principles	
	New Public Management	New Public Service
Who is served	Customer	citizen
The Role of Government	Directing: being a catalyst for developing market power	Serve: negotiate and be in the interests of the community, addressing common values.
Mechanisms to achieve goals	Create mechanisms and incentive structures to achieve policy objectives through private institutions and civil society.	Building coalitions and cooperation of government, private and civil society institutions, to meet mutually agreed needs.
Accountability approach	Directed by the market, personal decisions result in production that the customer/society wants	Multi-aspect, public services must meet legal requirements, community values, political norms, professional and citizen interests
Administrative discretion	Broader, to meet entrepreneurial goals	Discretion is required but limited by the principle of accountability
Organizational structure	Decentralised with ultimate control remaining in the hands of public institutions	Collaborative, with shared leadership, both internally and externally

Basic motivational public service	Entrepreneurial spirit, ideological desire to reduce the size of government	Service to the community, the desire to contribute to society.
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Source: Denhardt and Denhardt (2003:28-29)

The roots of the New Public Service (NPS) can be traced to various ideas about democracy that have been put forward by Dimock (1992), Dahl (2001) and Waldo (1953), which include:

1. Theories about civic democracy; The need for citizen involvement in policy making and the importance of deliberation to build solidarity and commitment to avoid conflict.
2. Community and civil society models; Accommodating to the role of civil society by building social trust, social cohesion and social networks in democratic governance.
3. The theory of humanist organization and new state administration; State administrations should focus on organizations that value human beings and respond to human values, justice and other social issues.
4. Postmodern state administration; Prioritizing dialogue (discourse) on theory in solving public problems rather than using a one best way perspective.

The new public service perspective starts from the recognition of citizens and their very important position for democratic governance. Citizen identity is not only seen as a matter of self-interest but also involves values, beliefs and concern for others. Citizens are positioned as owners of government and are able to act together to achieve something better. The public interest is no longer viewed as an aggregation of private interests, but rather as a result of public dialogue and engagement in the search for common values and common interests (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2003: 30-31).

The new public service perspective requires the role of public administrators to involve the public in government and serve the community. In carrying out this task, public administrators recognize the complex layers of responsibility, ethics, and accountability in a democratic system. Responsible administrators must involve the community not only in the planning but also in the implementation of programs to achieve community goals. This must be done not only to create a better government but also in accordance with democratic values. Thus, the job of the public administrator, according to Denhardt, is no longer directing or manipulating incentives, but service to the community.

Denhardt & Denhardt (2003: 30-33) then presented a number of new public service principles. These principles are: First, serve citizens, not customers. Because the public interest is the result of a dialogue about shared values rather than an aggregation of individual self-interest, public servants do not merely respond to customer demands but instead focus on building trust and collaboration with and among citizens. Second, seek the public interest. Public administrators must contribute to building the common public interest. The goal is not to find quick solutions directed by individual choices but to create common interests and shared responsibilities. Third, value citizenship over entrepreneurship. The public interest is better run by public servants and citizens who have a commitment to giving back to society than it is run by entrepreneurial managers who act as if public money is their own. Fourth, think strategically, act democratically. Policies and programs to meet the public interest can be achieved effectively and responsibly through collective efforts and collaborative processes. Fifth, recognize that accountability is not simple. In this perspective, public servants should be more concerned than market mechanisms. In addition, public servants must also comply with laws and regulations, social values, political norms, professional standards, and the interests of citizens. Sixth, serve rather than steer. It is important for public servants to use leadership based on shared values rather than controlling or directing society towards new values. Seventh, value people, not just productivity. Public organizations and their networks are more likely to achieve long-term success if they are run through a process of collaboration and shared leadership based on respect for all.

Table 3: OPA, NPM, and NPS differentiation

Aspects	Old Public Administration	New Public Management	New Public Service
Theoretical basis and Foundations of epistemology	Theory of politicsk	Economic theory	Democratic theory
Rationality and models of Human behavior	administrative man	economic man	Strategic rationality or formal raciality (political, economic and organizational)
Concept Public Interest	The public interest is politically explained and expressed in the rule of law	The public interest represents the aggregation of individual interests	Public interest is the result of dialogue Wide range of values
Responsiveness Public bureaucracy	Clients & constituent	Customer	Citizen's
The role of government	Rowing	Steering	Serving
Goal achievement	Government bodies	Private and nonprofit organizations	Coalition of public, nonprofit and private organizations
Accountability	Administrative hierarchy with a firm level	Work according to the will of the market (customer wishes)	Multifaceted: accountability laws, values, communities, political norms, professional standards
Administrative discretion	Limited discretion	Discretion is widely exercised	Discretion is needed but limited and responsible
Organizational structure	Marked bureaucratic with top-down authority	Decentralization of organizations with ultimate control vested in the agents	Collaborative structure with shared ownership internally and externally
Assumptions against Employee Motivation and administrator	Salary and benefits, Protection	Entrepreneurial spirit	Public service with the desire to serve the community

Source: Denhardt and Denhardt (2003: 28-29)

However, NPS is a relatively new paradigm in the study of public administration. NPS is rooted in civic democracy theory, community and civil society models, humanist organization theory and new state administration and postmodern state administration. NPS has different characteristics with OPA and NPM. NPS seeks to make up for the shortcomings in the OPA and NPM paradigms by offering a number of options. The essence of the NPS paradigm is to reposition the role of the state and government in providing public services to the community.

This new paradigm of public administration causes a pattern of relations between the state and society, which emphasizes more on the interests of society. As a result, the state is required to provide services to society better and more democratically. The same understanding is given by Denhardt that the new paradigm of public services (New Public Services Paradigm) is more directed at "democracy, pride and citizen". It further says that "Public servants do not delever customer service, they delever democracy". Therefore, democratic values, citizenship and service to the public interest must be seen as fundamental norms in the administration of public administration.

However, in the same book; The New Public Service Denhardt and Denhardt (2007:62) mention:

"Despite this complexity, there have been a variety of efforts to define public sector service quality. One especially comprehensive list developed for local government includes the following: 1. Convenience measures the degree to which government services are easily accessible and available to citizens. 2. Security measures the degree to which services are provided in a way that makes citizens feel safe and confident when using them. 3. Reliability assesses the degree to which government services are provided correctly and on time. 4. Personal attention measures the degree to which employees provide information to citizens

and work with them to help meet their needs. 5. Problem-solving approach measures the degree to which employees provide information to citizens and work with them to help meet their needs. 6. Fairness measures the degree to which citizens believe that government services are provided in a way that is equitable to all. 7. Fiscal responsibility measures the degree to which citizens believe local government is providing services in a way that uses money responsibly. 8. Citizen influence measures the degree to which citizens feel they can influence the quality of service they receive from the local government.”

However, the eight principles mentioned above are not authentic from Denhardt & Denhardt's opinion, but have been influenced by Carlson's (1995) views. Therefore, researchers use more than 7 NPS principles from Denhardt, this is because in the new public service, public services are based on democratic theory which teaches egalitarian and equal rights among citizens, because basically the people (demos) are the highest power holders (kratein), with logical consequences on the concept that since in its status in nature, Even to their status as citizens, these human beings have rights that because of their basic nature will not be possible to be taken over, denied and/or violated (inalienable, inderogable, inviolable) by anyone in power. In fact, these rulers must be seen as officials who obtain their legitimate power because of the mandate of citizens through a public contract, a noble agreement of the nation whose entire contractual substance will be realized in the form of a constitution (Wignjosoebroto, 2005: 11).

2.2. Building Permit

Theoretically, the government bureaucracy has three main functions, namely; service function, development function, and general government function. The three functions of the government bureaucracy show that public services carried out by local governments are very broad in scope, namely services that produce public good, such as roads, bridges, markets and others, and services that produce laws or policies (regulatory functions), which must be obeyed by the community such as permits, KTP, SIM, IMB, and others (Kurniadi & Suryadi, 2020).

According to Sutedi (2011: 200), the purpose of building permits is so that buildings erected by the community can be well organized and meet the requirements, suitable for use, and do not damage the environment. Efforts to realize city development or development programs and the benefits of urban space in an optimal, balanced and harmonious manner in order to create orderly and orderly regional conditions in accordance with applicable local regulations regarding building permits. IMB is given and issued by the regional head to building owners to build new, change, expand, reduce, and maintain buildings in accordance with applicable administrative and technical requirements. The permit to build a building which includes research activities on the layout and design of the building, supervision of its construction implementation to remain in accordance with the applicable spatial plan and technical plan of the building while taking into account the Basic Building Coefficient (KDB), Building Area Coefficient (KLB), Building Height Coefficient (KKB) includes inspection in order to meet the safety requirements for those who occupy the building.

Building permits are one of the legal products to realize a certain order so as to create order, security, safety, comfort, as well as legal certainty. Building permits will legalize a building that is planned in accordance with a predetermined spatial layout. In addition, the existence of a building permit shows that the construction plan of the building can also be accounted for with the intention of mutual interest. The provisions issued by the government have their respective functions. Similarly, the provisions on licensing have functions, namely: (a) as an orderly function, intended so that permits or any permits or places of business, buildings and other forms of community activities do not conflict with each other, so that order in every aspect of community life can be realized; (b) as a regulatory function, it is intended that existing permits can be carried out in accordance with their designation, so that there is misuse of permits that have been granted, in other words, this regulatory function can also be referred to as a function owned by the government (Amelia, 2021).

2.3. Thinking Framework

The frame of mind in the study is as follows:

Figure 1: Research Thinking Framework

3. Research Methodology

The research method used is qualitative methods. The qualitative method is seen as more relevant and suitable because it aims to explore and understand what is hidden behind the phenomenon. While the technique used is a case study, that is, a way of collecting data from several informants that is directly related to the focus of this research (Creswell, 2003: 67).

The operational design in this study uses the Denhardt & Denhardt Theory approach (2003: 190):

Table 4: Dimensions and Parameters

NO	DIMENSION	PARAMETERS	PARAMETER INDICATORS
1	serve citizens, not customers	The government serves the people as citizens not as customers	1) Measure the extent to which public services are easily accessible and available to citizens 2) Measure the extent to which public services are provided in a way that makes citizens feel safe and confident when using the services provided 3) Assess the extent to which the reliability of public services provided correctly and on time 4) Measure the extent to which the apparatus provides personal information attention to citizens and works with citizens to help meet their needs 5) Approach problem solving by measuring the extent to which apparatuses provide information to citizens and work with them to help meet their needs

NO	DIMENSION	PARAMETERS	PARAMETER INDICATORS
			<p>6) Measure the extent to which citizens believe that the government delivers public services in a way that is fair to all</p> <p>7) Measure the extent to which citizens trust local governments in providing public services by using funds responsibly</p> <p>8) Measure the extent to which citizens feel they can influence the quality of public services they receive from local governments</p>
2	Seek the public interest	The government must put the public interest first	<p>1) The apparatus helps citizens to articulate the public interest</p> <p>2) The apparatus must work to ensure that citizens are given a voice at every stage of government, not just in electoral politics. The apparatus has a unique and very important responsibility to engage with citizens and create a public dialogue forum</p>
3	Value citizenship and public service above entrepreneurship	The value of citizenship and public service over entrepreneurship	1) The apparatus no longer relies on management control skills, but rather on facilitation, negotiation, and conflict resolution skills
4	Think strategically, act democratically	Think strategically, act democratically	<p>1) All parties implement programs that will move in the desired direction</p> <p>2) Government can encourage citizen pride and civic responsibility</p> <p>3) Creating opportunities for participation and collaboration in achieving common goals</p> <p>4) Open and accessible government at all stages of the public policy process</p>
5	Recognize that accountability isn't simple	The government recognizes that accountability is not simple	1) An inherent accountability in public law relating to democratic safeguards, constitutional government should have an equal place on privatization of policy
6	Serve rather than steer	Serving rather than directing	<p>1) Identify challenges through diagnosing the value at stake and unraveling future problems</p> <p>2) Adapting work using the analogy of a <i>pressure cooker</i>, or staying hot without blowing up the vessel</p> <p>3) Identify actual issues and concentrate on those actual issues</p> <p>4) Develop responsibility for public issues</p>
7	Value people, not just productivity	The value of people is not just productivity	<p>1) The value of people is not just productivity, public organizations and networks in which they participate are more likely to succeed in the long run if they are operated through a process of collaboration and shared leadership based on respect for all people</p> <p>2) In its approach to management and organization, the new public service emphasizes the importance of management through people. Productivity system improvement, process reengineering, and performance measurement are seen as important tools in designing management systems</p> <p>3) The public service shows that rational efforts such as controlling human behavior tend to fail in the long run if at the same time not enough attention is paid to the values and interests of each member of an organization</p>

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. *Serve Citizens, Not Customers*

4.1.1. Government Services Easily Accessible or Not

The Bekasi City Investment and One-Stop Integrated Services Agency (DPMPTSP) has a Silat service, which is an integrated online licensing service. This SILAT application was created to provide convenience and speed of licensing for the community. The SILAT application stands for Integrated Licensing Service System, a smart phone-based program. Through the Silat application, the hotel and restaurant business sector will easily get business licenses anytime and anywhere online. Thus, with the SILAT program, it is hoped that permit applicants will not have to bother queuing for a long time at service counters in the management of permits. With the application of technology in bureaucratic services, it is hoped that it will not only provide convenience and speed for the community, but also to reduce illegal levy practices in the community.

Unfortunately, it turns out that this convenience cannot be enjoyed by all parties, some people consider that the existence of SILAT does not guarantee easy access to services as promised. The SILAT application, which has been considered as an effort by the government as an effort to position the community as citizens with various conveniences through technological assistance related to easy access to services for citizens, is considered to have no significant impact. The SILAT application is not something new that can make it easier for hotel and restaurant managers to take care of licensing. It turns out that what has been launched still leaves a lot of homework to be done, including the SILAT application is often difficult to access and has not given confidence to the public that this system is running well. The difficulty in accessing the SILAT application requires the public to contact the officers at DPMPTSP. This condition certainly opens the gap for the occurrence of "deal-dela" to facilitate the process of making permits and usually things happen that are not in line with NPS principles. Moreover, as the informant said, often coordination with related agencies has not run as expected. Likewise, officers' understanding of online-based work systems and IT systems still needs to be improved. The same thing also happens on the part of the applicant community where one of the obstacles is the limitation of accessing the internet and lack of mastery of technology and limited tools. Therefore, if you use the NPS principle, it is clear that it is still not in line with the first NPS principle, which is to provide ease of service to the community as citizens and not as customers. Thus, the indicator that in providing services to the community as citizens by facilitating access, has not been implemented effectively.

4.1.2. Citizens Feel Safe or Not

From the various information obtained, it turns out that many citizens feel safer if they take care of permits face-to-face with officers, not through the SILAT application. This is because in addition to the application is often difficult to access as previously described there is also no dialogue, unlike if you take care of it directly, face to face, with officers. In fact, people feel less confident when using the SILAT application because those who serve it are not officers but the application system itself. If then viewed from the first principle of NPS, it is clear that treating the community as citizens becomes ineffective if services are carried out through the SILAT application because if there is an error then what will be blamed is that the system is in error or the network is not supporting. If this happens, it is clear that the SILAT application has not been able to provide adequate services.

The community feels safer if taking care of direct licensing face-to-face with perugas becomes more humane, if there is something that is not understood related to licensing can get a direct explanation from the officer, unlike if online, the explanation in the management of information licensing is in accordance with what is stated on the internet / mobile phone screen in the explanation. The data from the interview clearly illustrates that the SILAT application system is actually considered not to provide security for the community who take care of permits, in this case the Building Permit (IMB) and other permit management as revealed by the informant below:

“... The SILAT application does not guarantee a sense of security for people who take care of permits...”

The picture above shows that people actually feel safe doing something if they are served by humans again, not by application systems. This means that there is still distrust from some people towards the use of technology provided because of various things related to technical problems to the problem of changing mindsets. So that people feel less safe if they register a permit application through SIKAT. In line with this, the first principle of NPS, namely that the government serves the community as citizens, not as customers, with the second indicator, namely that the community feels safe with the services provided, is still a problem in DPMPTSP Bekasi City.

4.1.3. Timely Service

Accuracy in terms of completing service time is a problem that is often faced by DPMPTSP Bekasi City in serving the community. DPMPTSP Bekasi City in terms of punctuality in serving the community has been implemented in accordance with procedures, but in its implementation there are still several obstacles. The obstacles faced, for example, the apparatus concerned are on business or out of town, in addition to the usual obstacles regarding information system errors that can hinder the process of completing services to the community. Things that hinder punctuality clearly hinder the process of completing services from the apparatus to the community which results in public disappointment with the apparatus.

Based on information from informants, the efforts made by DPMPTSP Bekasi City always try to do good service to the community. This effort is carried out by correcting the shortcomings contained in DPMPTSP Bekasi City, including adding human resources who have professionalism in work and have expertise in information technology. So that the obstacles faced in terms of service to the community can be overcome and able to provide decisions and time consistency can be overcome. However, the various efforts made have not been able to improve government services to citizens in managing permits in a timely manner. Even though they have used the SILAT application and promised that the management in the licensing process can be completed in one week, it still cannot be kept. In taking care of the IMB permit application process, for example, many residents complained, having to go back and forth to clean up draft drawings of the floor plan of the building or house to be built. Many people feel disappointed with this untimely service, especially many people who know that punctuality in obtaining permits is often determined by closeness to officers. Not a few community members who take care of the final licensing rather than difficult, they leave this matter to unscrupulous officers to be resolved immediately, and this in practice incurs a lot of costs beyond the fees that should be paid officially.

From the picture above, it shows that citizens seen from the perspective of NPS are still not served as citizens, the factor of closeness to officers is one of the important factors in solving licensing problems in a timely manner. If this is seen using the first principle of NPS, it can be said that citizens who take care of licensing have not been positioned as the state but are still considered customers. This is evidenced by the lack of timely implementation of parameters as one of the indicators of the first NPS principle.

4.1.4. Fulfillment of Information Needs by Government Apparatus

From various information, it turns out that information about IMB is obtained only from the internet or from information about his brothers who have taken care of IMB, the results of questions. For the community requesting permits, the information provided by the DPMPTSP apparatus is very lacking, this can be seen from the informant's statement below:

“... DPMPTSP employees do not actively provide the information needed by citizens”.

This shows that DPMPTSP officers or employees do not play an active role in providing information to the public. If this is seen using the first principle of NPS, it can be said that residents who take care of permits have not obtained the information services needed, so it can be said that people who manage permits have not been positioned as citizens but are still considered customers. Thus, it can be conveyed by researchers that employees or state civil servants who work at DPMPTSP Bekasi City do not actively provide information needed by the community, in this case it is the community who is taking care of permits.

The picture above shows the concept of NPS as an analytical knife used in this study, it can be said that how can the community be said to have been positioned as citizens if the data shows that those who become informants do not feel they get adequate information from DPMPTSP employees. In fact, in the NPS concept, providing information services to the community is an important requirement that must be fulfilled by the state civil apparatus, in this case DPMPTSP Bekasi City employees.

4.1.5. The state civil apparatus helps solve problems

Regarding licensing issues, the online system implemented has not worked well, has not been able to cut problems that often occur. The management of IMB Hotels and Restaurants is difficult and long, there are many complaints, even up to 1-2 years of taking care of permits. When it is difficult to penetrate the official, the entrepreneur then tries the help of unscrupulous people. But usually what helps isn't better and can't push the process any faster. There is still weakness in supervision and control of IMB Hotels and Restaurants, as evidenced by the continued development activities at several points that do not have IMB and violate the number of floor and basement permits.

From various informants there is a kind of information business carried out by DPMPTSP employees, what is meant by information business is that if there are obstacles faced by residents who want to take care of permits, the solution offered by the authorities is with a customer approach, namely people who take care of permits are given solutions to spend some money.

So far, there are indeed two pieces of information that are usually obtained from DPMPTSP employees. First, information that is normative as in line with applicable regulations, but there is a second type of information, namely confidential information that can only be known by the party who takes care of the permit with the employee who serves the permit management, usually a matter of cooperation in permit management, where employees or officers take care of the cleaning process to completion, while residents only provide enough money, Only then handover the files that have been sorted out with a number of previously promised uanh. There is a kind of mutualistic symbiosis, in which both parties equally need each other and are interdependent.

Thus, based on information obtained from various informants, all of whom stated the same thing, it can be conveyed by researchers that this fifth indicator, namely assistance in solving problems by the apparatus for residents who are carrying out permit management, has proven to be not implemented properly as the fifth indicator of the first principle of NPS.

Using the NPS concept, it can be said that the fifth indicator has clearly not been implemented by the state civil apparatus working in DPMPTSP, and therefore it clearly contradicts the first principle of NPS. That is, the government has not served the people as citizens not as customers.

4.1.6. Fair Service

Information from informants stated that DPMPTSP Bekasi City in this case tried to provide supporting facilities in providing services to the community. The supporting facility in question is the SILAT application which serves to make it easier for the community to apply for permits. In addition, the SILAT application can be used as a form of justice given by DPMPTSP Bekasi City because it is to prevent convoluted brokering and licensing practices.

Every community who applies for a permit at DPMPTSP Bekasi City gets equitable justice regarding the procedure for applying for a permit, the suitability of requirements with the type of service, the certainty or clarity of officers who provide services, the accuracy of implementation of service schedules and a comfortable service unit environment. This condition shows that DPMPTSP Bekasi City in providing services prioritizes justice to every community who applies for a permit at DPMPTSP Bekasi City.

The information obtained by researchers from informants is precisely the services provided by the DPMPTSP apparatus carried out unfairly. The services provided to the community still discriminate both in terms of position

and social community of permit applicants. Thus, the services provided are still discriminatory. Of course, this condition is not expected by the community. Not only for upper-middle class entrepreneurs, but also for small and medium-sized businesses in licensing. Different treatment can be seen when dealing through third parties and by using official channels. Those who go through third parties make it easier and faster. While dealing with using official channels must be admitted to be slow. Official lines can take two to three weeks, while third-party passages can be completed in just one day. According to the informant, whether or not the service is fair depends on two things as said below:

“... Fair or unfair service that is felt depends on two things, namely by personal closeness with the apparatus or officers, and second, by how much money is prepared for officers in managing permits...”.

4.1.7. Service Improvement Constitution

From the various information obtained, people who are taking care of permits do not have access at all to contribute to providing advice or input in an effort to improve the quality of services provided by the apparatus. In fact, they are not sure that they can contribute to improving the quality of service because the position of the community who is taking care of licensing with the position of the apparatus that takes care of licensing is not the same, one is the party that is taken care of, the other party, namely the government, is the party that takes care of it.

The indicator that the community can influence the quality of services they receive from local governments has not been successfully felt by people who are taking care of permits. Even the community does not know how to do it if the community intends to contribute to improving the quality of service. This can be interpreted that the eighth indicator that cannot be felt by the community who makes or manages the permit indicates that the state civil apparatus working in DPMPTSP, has not succeeded in implementing the first NPS principle related to community contribution in efforts to improve service quality has not been implemented properly.

4.2. *Seek the public interest*

In providing IMB is not easy, it must go through several processes and specified requirements. But on the contrary, there are currently many phenomena related to the granting of Building Permits (IMB) by the Bekasi City Government that do not comply with the rules. Construction of one of the hotels in Bekasi City, where the Bekasi City Government only allows buildings up to 2 floors. But in reality the hotel built up to the 5th and 6th floors. By erecting the building will have an impact on environmental damage which can cause various environmental problems such as flooding.

Using the indicator that civil servants have an important role in helping citizens to articulate the public interest, it turns out that the duty of the state civil apparatus in helping citizens articulate their interests, has not been implemented. This happens because the DPMPTSP Bekasi City apparatus has various interests, therefore they still prioritize the interests of community members who have personal closeness to themselves as revealed by the informant below:

“... DPMPTSP apparatus has not been able to help articulate the public interest because what is clear is that they still prioritize the interests of individuals who have personal closeness to the apparatus....”

As a result, DPMPTSP officials have not had a real role in articulating the public interest. There are those of the bureaucratic apparatuses who ignore the work of serving, which is actually their responsibility. They lack initiative and creativity. There are even some of them who still want retribution. Of course, this condition contradicts the services related to realizing the principles of good and clean governance, and does not place the community as citizens who must be served.

The second principle of NPS is that government serves the public interest. From the data obtained, it can then be stated that the government has not created a dialogue forum, especially to discuss the quality of services provided and in an effort to accommodate input from the public as input for service improvement.

In relation to the government must prioritize the public interest, in this case providing services to the subjects of IMB Hotels and Restaurants, it can be traced through how the DPMPTSP Bekasi City apparatus interprets the importance of the government must prioritize the public interest, as well as how the IMB subjects respond who get and feel the services provided by the DPMPTSP Bekasi City apparatus.

Whereas The public interest is the result of a dialogue about share values rather than the aggregation of individual self-interest (Denhardt, 2003).

4.3. Value citizenship and public service above entrepreneurship

From various information, it is obtained that the DPMPTSP apparatus still prioritizes entrepreneurship, even though the value of citizenship and public service should be above entrepreneurship, as one of the principles of NPS. There are still many apparatuses who think and act profit and loss in giving priority to services, should be value citizenship and public service above entrepreneurship.

The New Public Service views citizen involvement in government processes as more important than government driven by entrepreneurial spirit. The New Public Service argues that the public interest is better when formulated and developed by the apparatus together with citizens who have a commitment to make a meaningful contribution to life together.

The DPMPTSP Bekasi City apparatus has not provided public services using a citizenship approach but still uses an entrepreneurial approach. The citizenship approach places the public as the owner of sovereignty, while the entrepreneurial approach is to place the public as an object of income because entrepreneurs always calculate profits and losses.

4.4. Think strategically, act democratically

4.4.1. Implementing Programs that will Move in the Desired Direction

Implementing the program towards the direction that has been set is the first indicator for the fourth principle of NPS, namely thinking strategically through democratic actions that must be carried out by the government apparatus. Thinking strategically and acting democratically in the system of government is usually expressed in the form of policy.

From the information obtained through informants, it is known that the program to be achieved is actually carried out through practical thinking and pragmatic timing. In other words, the DPMPTSP apparatus still thinks easily, and prioritizes practicality. Therefore, it is not surprising that DPMPTSP does not see any strategic thinking efforts from the apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City in implementing the program to be achieved, nor does it see the form of democratic actions through dialogue in an effort to implement the program to be achieved. In fact, policies and programs that are initiated strategically are in an effort to answer public needs so that the services provided can be implemented effectively and responsively.

4.4.2. Encouraging Citizen Pride and Civic Responsibility

From information obtained through informants, it is known that the local government, in this case represented by the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, has never made efforts to encourage community pride and public responsibility, in this case civil society with an interest in obtaining IIMB building permits).

The government through the state civil apparatus working in DPMPTSP, has never been seen carrying out efforts through any program to build public pride so that a sense of pride arises as a community that respects its sovereignty, for example through discussion forums, or other efforts, such as giving awards to the public who take care of their IMB.

In fact, the root of the NPS concept is democracy, and hence, building a government must be together with the public. More specifically, good governance must involve 3 key components, namely the public, the private sector, and the government itself. Thus, these three key components must be equally involved in the governance process. That is why it is important to encourage the birth of citizen pride as part of good governance stakeholders so that the public, in this case citizens, in NPS terms are called citizens, feel their responsibility in managing government.

4.4.3. Creating Opportunities for Participation and Collaboration in Achieving Common Goals

The third indicator for the fourth NPS principle is that the government should create opportunities for participation and collaboration (cooperation) in achieving common goals. In reality, as information obtained from informants that opportunities for participation and collaboration to achieve common goals actually already exist as stated by informants below:

“... The opportunity exists, but unfortunately, the opportunity is more ceremonial and formalistic, because in the end, it is still the government that has the authority to regulate all the results of the Musrenbang...”

From what is obtained in the field, researchers can convey that regional development deliberation activities (Musrenbang) as a means to prioritize the public interest, are more carried out as ceremonial-formalistic in nature. Although it must be admitted that through a series of regulations, the government has tried to prioritize the public interest while encouraging the application of a participatory approach in regional development planning, as well as opening space for community involvement in the process of local government management. But in general, the government has not reduced its party dominance and given up some or given opportunities to the people as citizens to play an active role. The government still uses the Government Paradigm where the role of the government is still dominant and has not shifted towards the Governance Paradigm, which is a paradigm in NPS that emphasizes how the government interacts in equal roles with the community as citizens in meeting the needs of its citizens.

4.4.4. Open and Accessible Government at All Stages of the Policy Process

The fourth indicator for the fourth NPS principle is that government should be open and accessible in all levels of the policy process. Normatively, the government in this case represented by the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, indeed always conveys its mission of openness, that the Bekasi City Government is an open government so that the public can access various programs and even access every stage of policy making. However, the facts on the ground show that what is said and what is done by DPMPTSP officers is very different. Normatively and formalistically, policy makers in Bekasi City, in this case state civil servants working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, often state that they are open and always involve the public. But in practice this is not the case. Thus, so far the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City has been ambiguous. First, formally and normatively declare itself as part of local government that is open and opens the widest access for the public to know all programs and all stages of policy making. Second, in practice, because the position of the state civil apparatus, in this case those who work at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, is the party who has the authority, so in reality, what is conveyed normatively and formally, is not in accordance with reality. This means that from the NPS side, it shows that the state civil apparatus in DPMPTSP is still based on a legal-normative approach, not only at the institutional level but also at the apparatus level that directly provides services to permit applicants. In fact, when the DPMPTSP apparatus operationally provides directly to permit applicants, they should also be able to think strategically without having to violate applicable regulations.

4.5. *Recognize that accountability isn't simple*

Accountability of public services must be built in line with the development of a multi-cultural society. The construction of accountability for the implementation of public services is carried out by providing participation space to accommodate community demands. By accommodating the interests and needs of the community, it is hoped that a joint commitment will be built in the implementation of public services. Mutual commitment can be fostered by putting aside the interests and egos of official agencies in the state institutional structure.

Accountability for the implementation of public services involving parties with the aim of building a joint commitment in the space of community participation, namely between service providers and community citizens, will lead parties to a more responsive public service delivery accountability process. However, accountability is not an easy thing and easy to do, accountability cannot be considered completed just by making periodic reports. That is why, one of the principles of NPS states: recognize that accountability isn't simple.

4.6. Serve rather than steer

4.6.1. Identify Challenges Through Diagnosing Value at Stake, and Unraveling Problems That Will Arise

In relation to public services for community members, although various efforts to change the mind-set from being served to serving but even this depends on the will and desire of the Bekasi City DPMPTSP apparatus itself. The concept of serve rather than steer (serving rather than directing) although it has been widely discussed, has also not been able to change the main function of government to serve its citizens and not direct. It seems that in accordance with the principles of NPS, public services must be developed based on service values, so that the respect of the Bekasi City DPMPTSP apparatus for citizens as sovereign owners can be realized in the form of services that are in accordance with the demands of citizens. Thus, researchers can say that the government has not seen anticipating the challenges that will arise and what possible values are at stake when these challenges actually come and we must face them.

While related to the second point, namely the government should be able to parse problems that will arise or anticipate future problems, information is obtained from informants that how can the government describe problems in detail if identifying problems is not done. Therefore, the researcher concludes that these two main things, namely the first point, the government should be able to identify challenges through diagnosis, should be able to identify challenges through the diagnosis of the value at stake, and the second point, the government should be able to parse problems that will arise or anticipate future problems. These two main things have not been implemented by the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, so that public services have not been effective.

4.6.2. Work Adaptations Using the Pressure Cooker Analogy, or Stay Hot Without Blowing Up the Vessel

Based on the information obtained by researchers as mentioned above, researchers can convey that the signals that have been mentioning that state civil servants who work in organizations called bureaucracy, tend to be engrossed in themselves. Not only because they are busy concentrating on carrying out their work routines so that they no longer have the energy of thought and time to adapt work based on the demands of the community, but indeed it is related to public services in the ranks of the state civil apparatus whose loyalty is directed to superiors and not to the community. Therefore, it is not uncommon for the apparatus to still want to run the government in the old way, which is not in line with the principles of NPS.

4.6.3. Identify Actual Issues and Concentrate on Those Actual Issues

The SILAT application may be the result of identification of various actual problems in the licensing process, but whether then the government can concentrate on managing this SILAT application which is felt has not been proven because the existing application often errors when accessed. Coupled with the absence of a change in mind-set both from the DPMPTSP apparatus itself and the community. Another informant highlighted that the actual issue was a matter of public demands that were increasingly expected to improve service quality because the presence of various information technology-based applications was just a tool as conveyed by the informant of the IMB license applicant below:

“... Information technology-based applications are merely tools and therefore not an indicator of the improvement of public services...”

It was even said by subsequent informants that there was no evidence available to the public regarding the government's efforts to identify the actual issue and concentrate on the actual issue. Because so far there has been no public involvement to work together with the government to try to identify and concentrate on actual issues related to the interests of existing stakeholders. Moreover, there is no evidence that the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City has identified and at the same time concentrated on issues that develop in the midst of society.

4.6.4. Develop responsibility for public issues

According to the informant of the state civil apparatus working in DPMPTSP, it has never been seen to streamline its public services. Apparatuses working at DPMPTSP always only focus on their respective goals, so that the problem of improving the quality of public services is ignored. It is not surprising, therefore, that the government's responsibility to help solve public problems has not been seen until now.

From these data, it can be seen that the state civil apparatus that works in DPMPTSP has not seen its efforts to develop its responsibility for the problems faced by the public, especially through efforts to streamline public services, within the DPMPTSP Bekasi City.

4.7. *Value people, not just productivity*

4.7.1. Shared Collaboration and Leadership Process

Leadership in the New Public Service is shared leadership where leadership control is not centralized in the hands of superiors but involves many people, many groups. The leadership position here is not as an owner but a public servant or public servant (servant, not owner).

In relation to the process of collaboration and joint leadership, it does not appear to be practiced by the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, as evidenced in all sections, all employees refer to their respective superiors. The process of collaboration and joint leadership, in this case between the community or Bekasi City residents who are taking care of IMB with the state civil apparatus serving in DPMPTSP Bekasi City, has not shown any collaboration built by placing community members who take care of IMB as citizens. The state civil apparatus in charge of DPMPTSP Bekasi City, often still places residents who take care of IMB as customers. This happens, because the concentration of the apparatus prioritizes providing service satisfaction to their superiors, rather than to the public who take care of IMB. As a result, a process of collaboration and shared leadership based on respect for all people according to NPS principles has not yet taken place.

4.7.2. Performance Measurement

Based on data obtained in the field, it is known that performance measurement does not appear to be practiced by state civil servants working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, it is proven that none of the informants obtained a copy of the report on performance measurement. According to informants, so far, performance reports are only to be reported to superiors, and there is no awareness to be conveyed to the public, this is the culture that exists in the bureaucracy, including in DPMPTSP until now. Furthermore, it is also known that DPMPTSP's performance measurement related to public services has no evidence. This means, until now there is no form of public service measurement report submitted to the public or the public as part of good governance.

From the picture above, it shows that performance measurement may actually have been carried out, as is the obligation of government agencies, but when whether the performance measurement report is also submitted to the public or not, this is not obtained, that is, information on the performance measurement of apparatus at DPMPTSP Bekasi City, information is not obtained by Bekasi City residents who are taking care of IMB.

4.7.3. The Value of Each Member's Importance

From the various information obtained, the interests of each community member who manages IMB, namely getting fast and fair service, only obtained the service. While speed and fairness in the provision of services are not obtained at all, that is, getting a "Yes" but a question of whether the service provided is done quickly and fairly the answer is "No".

From the picture above, it shows that the value of the interests of each member, in this case, community members or Bekasi City residents who are taking care of IMB, are neglected by the state civil apparatus working at DPMPTSP Bekasi City. This happens, meaning that the neglect of these values occurs, because of the concentration of the apparatus on its service, which is important to serve. Meanwhile, related to the speed of service and fairness of service, which are values of the interests of community members who take care of IMB, are not considered.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, it can be concluded that the public services of the Bekasi City DPMPTSP apparatus in making Hotel and Restaurant Building Permits (IMB) are still ineffective. This is due to the non-application of the principles of *the New Public Service*.

In the aspect of *Serve citizens*, not customers or the government serves the community as citizens not as customers, people are still considered customers are not considered citizens. In fact, the apparatus is still like selling services to consumers as customers.

In the aspect of *Seek the public interest* or the government must prioritize the public interest, still prioritizing individual interests. In fact, the apparatus still prioritizes service to individuals who have a personal approach with the apparatus.

In the aspect of Value citizenship and public service above entrepreneurship or the value of *citizenship and* public service above entrepreneurship, it still prioritizes entrepreneurship. In fact, the apparatus still thinks and acts profit and loss in giving priority to services.

In the aspect of *Think strategically*, act democratically or think strategically, act democratically, the DPMPTSP apparatus still does not think strategically and has not acted democratically. In fact, the apparatus still thinks technically and acts on commands.

In the aspect of *Recognize that accountability isn't simple* or the government recognizes that accountability is not simple in fact accountability is considered simple, enough to exist / make reports. Even though accountability is not as simple as submitting periodic reports.

In the aspect of *Serve*, rather than *steer* or serve, rather than direct, the apparatus still often directs rather than serves. In fact, the apparatus directs more "this must be the case" to people who intend to apply for permits.

In the *aspect of Value* people, not just productivity or value people is not just productivity, the apparatus is still oriented to results or productivity. In fact, the apparatus is still oriented towards achieving targets.

References

- Achyar, Rachmat. (2001). Study of the Work Culture of Employees in the Organization of the Regional Revenue Office of the Special Capital Region of Jakarta. *MM Agribusiness*. IPB
- Akhmaddhian, Suwari. (2012). The Effect of Bureaucratic Reform on Investment Licensing in the Regions (Case Study in Bekasi City Government). *Jurnal Dinamika Hukum*. September 12 (3) 2012. Downloaded February 28, 2014, from the World Wide Web site <http://fh.unsoed.ac.id/sites/default/files/fileku/documents/JDH2012 /.pdf>
- Apdiansyah, Rakhmad. (2012). Implementation of Licensing and Non-Licensing Policy in Service. *Journal of Democracy & Regional Autonomy*, 10 (1) Juni 2012, 1-66. Downloaded February 28, 2014, from the World Wide Web site http://portalgaruda.org/download _article.php?article
- Apriyanti, Ira. (2008). Work Culture Among Argo-Entrepreneurs. Thesis Faculty of Agriculture. Putra Malaysia University, Malaysia.
- Asfiah, Nurul. (2009). The work culture of Islamic Hospital 'Aisyiyah Malang is an effort to improve the quality of public health services. *HUMANITY*. Volume IV. Number 2. March 2009: 96 – 107
- Barkow, Ben. (2002). Factors of Group Work Culture Which Influence the Safety
- Batinggi, Achmad., dan Ahmad, Badu. (2008). *IPEM4429 General Service Management Subject Book*.
- Bazarah. (2023). Implementation of Good Governance in Public Services (Literacy Study of Public Service Problems in Indonesia). *Journal of Administration & Policy PREDICTION*. Vol.22(1), 35-43. <http://ejurnal.untag-smd.ac.id/index.php/PD/article/download/6861/pdf>
- Caiden, G.E. (1991). Administrative Reform Comes Age. New York, N.Y., de
- Creswell, J.W. (2003). Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Method Approaches. Thousand Oaks. Sage.
- Darma (penerjemah). (1993). Personnel Management. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- David, Hell. (2004). Democracy and Global Order. Jogjakarta, Student Library.
- Davis, Keith., dan Kohn W. Newstrom., Agus Dharma (pent). (1996). Behavior in Organizations. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Denhardt, R.B., dan Denhardt, J.V. (2000). The New Public Service: Service Rather than Steering. *Public Administration Review* 60 (6).
- Denhardt, R.B., dan Denhardt, J.V. (2003). The New Public Service: An Approach to Reform. *International Review of Public Administration* 8 (1).
- Depdagri-LAN. (2007). Public Service Policy Module. Public Service Technical Training, Accountability and Quality Management. Jakarta: LAN.
- Djahiri, A. Kosasih. (1985). VCT Affective Values-Moral Teaching Strategies and Games in VCT. Bandung: IKIP
- Dryzek, John. (2000). Deliberative Democracy And Betond : Liberals, Critics, Contestations. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Dryzek, John S, dkk (eds). (2006). The Oxford Handbook of Political Theory. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Dwiyanto, Agus. (2006). Public Bureaucracy Reform in Indonesia. Yogyakarta: Gajahmada University Press.
- Efriza, (2008). Political Science. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Engkus., Azan., Ainyna Rachmadianty., Hanif Alliadzar., dan Fitri, Anisa Tiara. Realizing Good Governance through Public Services. *Journal of DIALECTICS: Journal of Social Sciences*. Vol 19 No 1. <http://jurnaldialektika.com/index.php/piani/article/download/62/54/74>
- Etzioni Amitai. (1985). Modern Organizations. University of Indonesia (UI-Press) and Bradjaguna Library. Jakarta,
- Farnham, D., dan S. Horton. (1993). The Political Economy of Public Sector Change, in D. Farham and S. Horton, eds. *Managing The New Public Services*. London: The Macmillan Press Ltd.
- Frederickson George, H. (2006). New State Administration. LP3ES. Jakarta, 2003 Hoadley, Mason H, Quo Vadis Indonesian State Administration, Graha Ilmu Yogyakarta,
- Gaffar, Afan. (2006). Indonesian Politics: The Transition to Democracy. Yogyakarta: Gruyter.
- Haida, Achmad Nur., Saleh, Chairul., dan Adiono, Romula. (2013). One-Stop Integrated Service as an Effort to Improve Licensing Services (Study at the Kediri City Licensing Service Office). *Journal of Public Administration*, 1 (2), 8-14. Downloaded February 28, 2014, from the World Wide Web <http://administrasipublik.studentjournal.ub.ac.id/index.php>
- Hardiman, Fresco Budi. (2009). Deliberative Democracy. Yogyakarta: Canisius Publishers.
- Hardiyansyah. (2018). Quality of Public Services, Their Concept, Dimensions, Indicators, and Implementation. <https://www.gavamedia.net/produk-245-kualitas-pelayanan-publik-konsep-dimensi-indikator-dan-implementasinya.html>
- Harjanto, N.T. Budi. (1998). Studies of Political Development : From Modernization to Democratization. In *CSIS ANALYSIS* Year XXVII No. 2, April – June.

- Hasibuan., dan Malahayu SP. (1999). *Organization and Motivation: The Basis of Productivity Improvement*. Jakarta: Aksara.
- Hell, David. 2004. *Democracy and Global Order*. Jogjakarta, Student Library.
- Henry, Nicholas. (1995). *Public Administration and Public Affairs (Sixth Edition)*. Prentice-Hall Englewood Cliffs, New Jersey.
- Herawati, Desy.(2011). Planning to improve the quality of licensing services at the Padang City Government. Downloaded March 1, 2014, from the World Wide Web site <http://pasca.unand.ac.id/id/wp-content/uploads/2011/09/ARTIKEL12.pdf>.
- <http://www.menpan.go.id/index.php/liputan-media-index/143-kualitas-pelayanan-publik-rendah> [16-3-2011]
- Huntington, Samuel P. (2009). *Political participation in developing countries*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Ibrahim, Amin. (2008). *Theory and Concept of Public Service and Its Implementation*. Bandung: Mandar Maju.
- Ibrahim, M. A., Pangkey, M., & Dengo, S. (2021). Public Services During the Covid19 Pandemic at the Kema Sub-district Office, North Minahasa Regency. *Journal of Public Administration*. Vol 7(108). <https://ejournal.unsrat.ac.id/v3/index.php/JAP/article/view/35078>
- Ihalauw John JOI, (1985). *Build Theory*. Satya Wacana Christian University, Salatiga,
- Kahar, Irawaty A, (2003). *Work Culture and Innovative Attitude as Supporting Factors for the Performance of College Library Librarians in Padang*. Postgraduate Thesis of Padang State University
- Kartasasmita, Ginandjar, (2007). *Revitalization of Public Administration in Realizing Sustainable Development*. Paper, Delivered at the 44th Graduation Ceremony of the College of Administrative Sciences of the State Administration Institute, Jakarta,
- Kartiwa, A. dan Nugraha, (2012). *Manage Government Authority*. Bandung: Lepsindo.
- Keban, Yeremias T. (2004). *Six Strategic Dimensions of Public Administration, Concepts, Theories and Issues*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media.
- Keban, Yeremias T. (2008). *Six Strategic Dimensions of Public Administration: Concepts, Theories and Issues*. Yogyakarta: Gava Media Publishers.
- Kepmenpan No. 25/KEP/M.PAN/04/2002
- Decree of the State Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 / KEP / M.PAN / 7/2003 concerning General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services
- Khun Thomas, S. (1993). *The Role of Paradigm in the Science Revolution*. Publisher PT Remaja Rosdakarya, Bandung,
- Koentjaraningrat. (2002). *Culture of Mentality and Development*. Jakarta : PT. Gramedia.
- Kompas Forum 26-02-2012
- Koran Jakarta, Kamis 4 November 2010
- Kurniadi., Ibrahim, Syafei., Badruzzaman., Purnama, Harris. (2023). Transformation of the Indonesian Government Bureaucracy. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*. 6(2), 20-30. <https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>. doi: 10.31014/aior.1991.06.02.407
- Legowo, T.A. (1996). *Revitalization of Indonesia's Political System*. Jakarta: Centre for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS) – Jakarta
- Legowo, Tommi A.. (1994). *Democratization: A Transformative Reflection on Power*. *Journal of Analysis*. Year XXIII No. 1.
- Lembaga Administrasi Negara. (2004). *Unitary State Administration System of the Republic of Indonesia (SANKRI)*. Book 3. Jakarta: LAN.
- Ling, L.H.M dan Chih-yu Shih. (1998). Confusianism with a Liberal Face : The Meaning of Democratic Politics in Post-Colonial Taiwan. *The Review of Politics*. Vol. 60 No. 1.
- Lovelock, Christopher H. (1991). *Service Marketing*. USA: Prentice Hall, Inc.
- Mahmudi. (2005). *Public Sector Performance Management*. Yogyakarta: UPP STIM YKPN
- Mahsyar, Abdul. (2013). Public Service Problems in Indonesia in Public Administration Perspective. *Journal of Authority*. Vol 1, No 2, October 2013. <https://journal.unismuh.ac.id/index.php/Otoritas/article/download/22/20>
- McKevitt, David. (1998). *Managing core public services*. Published by Blackwell Publishers in Oxford, Malden, Mass .
- Miles, Matthew B., A. Michael Huberman, (1992). *Qualitative Data Analysis*, Jakarta: UI. Press.
- Moenir, H.A.S. (2006). *Public Service Management in Indonesia*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara
- Mohamad, Ismail. (2017). *Improving the Quality of Government Apparatus Services through the Development of Service Standards and Community Satisfaction Index*. Center for Policy and Service Management Studies, State Administration Institute. <https://perpus.menpan.go.id/opac/detail-opac?id=1201>
- Mulgan, Geoff. (1995). *Politics in an Anti-Political Era*. Jakarta: Yayasan Obor Indonesia.
- Musgrave, Richard A., dan Peggy B. Musgrave. (1989). *State Finance in Theory and Practice*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Nasirin, Chairun. (2013). Public Administration Reform: A Conceptual Study. *Scientific Journal of Public Administration and Development*, Vol.4, No.2, July-December 2013
- Ndraha, Taliziduhu. (2003). *Kibernetology: The Science of New Government*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.

- Ndraha, Taliziduhu. (1997). *Organizational Culture*, Jakarta : PT. Rineka Cipta
- Ndraha, Taliziduhu. (2014). *Crucial Issues of Contemporary Public Administration*. Bandung: LEPSINDO.
- Noermijati., dan Raden Pamungkas Al Amin. (2010). Study of Core Organizational Culture Values and Commitment of Aiesec Local Committee Members Universitas Brawijaya Malang. *Journal of Management Applications, Volume 8*, Number 3, August 2010.
- Nurmandi, Achmad. (2010). *Public Service Management*. Yogyakarta: Sinergi Publishing of *Power Line Mainteners*. Toronto.
- Osborne dan Ted Gaebler. (1996). *Bureaucratic Entrepreneurship*, tr. Abdul Rasyid, Jakarta: Binaman Pressindo Library.
- Osborne, David and Ted Gaebler. 1992. *Reinventing Government*. PPM Jakarta 2003
- Osborne, David. Peter Plastrik. (2004). *Cutting red tape: five strategies towards entrepreneurial governance*. Jakarta: PPM. Student Library.
- Pamudji, S. (1994). *Professionalism of the state apparatus in order to improve public services*. Jakarta: Widyapraja Poerwadarminta, W.J.S. (1995). *Great Dictionary Indonesian*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- Pollitt, C. (2006). Performance management in practice: a comparative study of executive agencies. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory, Vol. 16 No. 1*, pp. 25-44.
- Prasetijo. (2020). *Good Governance and Sustainable Development*. in <http://prasetijo.wordpress.com>
- Prayitno, Widyo Yudo, (2004). *Work culture, ability and commitment of civil servants in the Civil Service Bureau of the Regional Secretariat of East Java Province*. Thesis of Postgraduate Program Airlangga University Surabaya.
- Purwanto, Erwan Agus. (2005). *Participatory Public Service in Agus Dwiyanto (editor). 2005. Realizing Good Governance through Public Services*. Yogyakarta: JICA collaborates with Gajah Mada University Press. Student Library.
- Rajab, Budi. (2013). *Lack of Application of the Concept of Good Governance in Government Order in the Era of Democratization. CSIS analysis. Vol 14 No 4. ISSN 1829-5908*
- Ratminto & Atik Septi Winarsih. (2007). *Service Management*. Yogyakarta: Student Center.
- Robbins, Stephen P, (1996). *Organizational Behavior-Concept, Controversies, Applications*. Jakarta: PT. Prenhallindo.
- Rohayatin, Titin., Warsito, Tulus., Pribadi, Ulung., Nurmandi, Achmad., Kumorotomo, Wahyudi., dan Suranto, Suranto. (2017). *Factors Causing the Not Optimal Quality of Public Service Delivery in Government Bureaucracy. Journal of Government Science Cakra Prabhu. Vol 1, No 01.* <https://ejournal.fisip.unjani.ac.id/index.php/jurnal-caraka-prabu/article/view/50>. **doi:** <https://doi.org/10.36859/jcp.v1i01.50>
- Rosenbloom, David H., Deborah H. Goldman dan Patricia W. Ingraham. (1963). *Contemporary Publik Administration*. New York : Mc-Graw Hill, 1994. Rosenstein-Rodan, Paul. "Notes on the Theory of the Big Push", dalam H.S. Ellis (ed.). *Economic Development for Latin America*. New York: St.Martin's,
- Rusli, Budiman. (2013). *Public Policy: Building a Responsive Public Service*. Bandung: Hakim Publishing
- Saefullah, Djadja. (1995). *Literature Review and Use of Literature Information in Thesis and Dissertation Writing*. Bandung:
- Saefullah, H. A. Djadja. (2008a). *Contemporary Thought of Public Administration Human Resource Management Perspectives in the Era of Decentralization*. Bandung: AIPI and PK2W Lemlit Unpad.
- Sedarmayanti. (2012). *Good Government & Good Corporate Governance*. Bandung: CV. Mandar Forward.
- Sembiring, Masana. (2012). *Organizational Culture and Performance*. Bandung: Fokusmedia.
- Senge, Peter. (1990). *The Fifth Discipline*. USA: Double Day.
- Setiadi (2009). *Implementation of the One-Stop Integrated Licensing Service Management Information System Policy (SIM-PPTSP) in Improving Building Licensing Services (a study on the Investment Agency and Integrated Licensing Services of the Bandung City Government for the January-May 2008 period)*. Downloaded February 28, 2014, from the World Wide Web <http://garuda.dikti.go.id/>
- Siagian, Sondang P. (2001). *Basic Framework of Administrative Science*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- Sinamo, J.H. (1998). *Looking for the Power Behind the Crisis*. Jakarta: Management.
- Thoha, Miftah. (2003). *Bureaucracy and Politics in Indonesia*. Jakarta: Rajagrafindo Persada. Sedarmayanti. 2012. *Good Government & Good Corporate Governance*. Bandung: CV. Mandar Forward.
- Triguno, (1999), *Work Culture – Creating an Environment Conducive to Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services*.
- Wasistiono, Sadu. (2001). *Local Government Management*. Bandung: Alqa Print.
- Wibowo, Eddy Kusponco. (2001). *Improve the Discipline and Professionalism of Civil Servants in order to Improve the Performance of Civil Servants*. In *Uncovering the Opportunities and Challenges of Public Administration*. Jakarta : LAN RI.
- Wignjosoebroto, Soetandyo. (2005). *Democracy and Human Rights*. in a paper delivered in the framework of Human Rights Training by the Center for Human Rights Studies, University of Surabaya, Thursday, June 30, 2005.

Zakiah, Siti S, (2005). Study of the Work Culture of Local Government Organizations in Kalimantan. LAN Samarinda.